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LEGAL BASES AND LIABILITY MECHANISMS FOR PROCESSING PATIENT HEALTH DATA IN GEORGIA: A COMPARISON WITH EUROPEAN STANDARDS

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Abstract

The present article examines the legal bases for processing patient personal data, especially health data, and the liability mechanisms in case of their violation in the context of medical activity. The research is based on normative-dogmatic and comparative-legal methods and combines European data protection standards, international human rights protection mechanisms and professional ethical norms, as well as Georgian national legislation and administrative practice.

The aim of the research is to systematically analyze the legal bases and liability framework for processing patient personal data in the context of medical activity, by identifying those legal mechanisms that ensure effective protection of patient data, and in case of violation - appropriate imposition of liability.

The normative model of technical and organizational obligations for health data processing in electronic systems is separately analyzed as a practical tool of legal control. The article structurally includes: (I) the status of health data; (II) the legal basis for data processing; (III) forms of liability and administrative response, including professional standards and regulation of electronic systems. The final part formulates recommendations for strengthening the real, and not only formal, provision of patient data protection and rights.

Keywords: health data; confidentiality; data processing; informed consent; public interest; professional ethics.

Introduction

In the modern healthcare system, the processing of patient personal data is one of the most sensitive and high-risk legal processes. Given the specifics of medical activity, patient health information includes data that are directly related to a person's private life and dignity. For this reason, patient health data is classified as a special category of personal data in modern legal systems and is subject to a strict legal protection framework.

The processing of patient personal data in medical activities is a legally regulated process that must be based on clearly defined legal grounds, professional standards and accountability mechanisms. Improper data processing may result in both a violation of the fundamental rights of the patient and the legal liability of the medical institution and personnel. Thus, the protection of patient data is considered not only in the context of protecting individual rights, but also in the context of public interest and patient safety.

The lawfulness of the processing of patient personal data cannot be limited to meeting formal requirements. It is necessary to assess the entire cycle of data processing - from data collection, storage and use, to their sharing and destruction. In this process, special importance is attached to the legal grounds for data processing, including professional obligations, public interest and informed consent of the patient, which does not constitute a universal or absolute guarantee for the lawful processing of data.

In the legal space of Georgia, the issue of the protection of patient personal data is regulated by both the legislation regulating the healthcare sector and the norms on the protection of personal data. However, practice shows that the relationship between data

protection and medical activities is often assessed fragmentarily, and the mechanisms of responsibility are inconsistent. Particularly problematic is the superficial understanding of the role of informed consent, when the formal existence of consent automatically equates to the legality of data processing, despite the neglect of other legal requirements.

Chapter 1. Health data as a special category of personal data

1.1. Legal basis for the special status of health data

Health data is a special category of personal data, the processing of which is legally subject to an enhanced protection regime due to their high sensitivity and direct connection with fundamental human rights. These data reflect the physical and mental state of a person, the history of medical interventions and health risks, which directly connects them to the principles of privacy and human dignity. Accordingly, the processing of health data is permissible only on strictly defined legal grounds and in compliance with the principle of proportionality, since their unlawful disclosure or use creates a real threat of discrimination, social stigmatization and violation of patient autonomy. The World Medical Association's Lisbon Declaration on the Rights of the Patient establishes a modern medical-legal standard based on patient autonomy and justice. The document ensures the patient's right to quality medical care, informed decision and consent, confidentiality of information and respect for dignity, thus considering patient rights as a unified system of

professional ethics and positive obligations of the state.¹

According to Article 8 of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, the protection of private and family life is a fundamental right, within the framework of which information about a person's health also falls. This provision prohibits arbitrary interference by public authorities with this right and only allows interference in exceptional cases when it is carried out on the basis of law and is necessary in a democratic society, including to ensure the legitimate aim of health protection. This standard in the context of the processing of health data means that such interference is permissible only under strict conditions of lawfulness, necessity and proportionality, which creates a legal basis for enhanced protection of these data.²

The case law of the European Court of Human Rights also confirms that health information belongs to the most intimate sphere of private life and must be protected.³

1.2. European legal framework for the protection of health data

Within the European legal framework for the protection of health data, the processing of special categories of personal data, including health data, is prohibited in principle, reflecting the particular sensitivity of the information in question and the high degree of potential impact on fundamental human rights. At the same time, the legal regulation provides for exceptional cases when the processing of such data is permitted on strictly defined legal grounds, including on the basis of the explicit consent of the data subject, in cases of necessity for the protection of life and health, for important objectives of public interest or in the process of medical diagnosis, treatment and management of healthcare systems. These exceptions are based on the principles of proportionality and purpose limitation and are associated with the existence of additional guarantees, such as the protection of professional secrecy and the application of appropriate organizational and technical security measures.⁴ Thus, the processing of health data is legally permissible only when it serves a legitimate purpose and the rights and interests of the data subject are adequately protected.

According to the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA) Data Protection Law Guidance, health data are considered not only direct medical information, such as diagnosis, data on treatment or medical interventions performed, but also

any information that directly or indirectly allows conclusions to be drawn about the physical or mental health of a person. Such data may include laboratory test results, genetic data, mental health records, information on the presence of chronic diseases or disabilities, as well as data related to the fact of the patient receiving medical care. This broad definition once again highlights the particular sensitivity of health data and justifies the existence of an enhanced legal protection regime for them.⁵

The Oviedo Convention considers health data as an integral part of the inviolability of private life and establishes the right of an individual to the protection of health information, as well as the right to know the data collected about him or her or, if he so wishes, to refrain from receiving them. At the same time, the Convention does not establish the absoluteness of health data protection: it allows restrictions on the exercise of rights only on the basis of law and only when this is necessary in a democratic society, including for legitimate public health purposes. As a result, the processing of health data is subject to the principles of lawfulness, purposefulness and proportionality.⁶

1.3. National Legal Framework for Health Data Protection

According to the Georgian legal framework, health data are considered a special category of personal data and are subject to enhanced legal protection. The Law of Georgia on Personal Data Protection defines health-related information, as well as genetic and biometric data, the processing of which is related to the unique identification of a natural person, as a special category of data. The aforementioned law broadly defines the concept of health data and includes not only information about the physical or mental health of a person, but also any data related to the fact of providing medical services, including in cases where such data indirectly allow conclusions to be drawn about the state of health. This normative approach reflects the legislator's assessment of the special sensitivity of health data and justifies the need for stricter legal protection for them. At the same time, the law considers the processing of special categories of data to be permissible only in the presence of strictly defined legal grounds and additional guarantees for the protection of the rights and interests of the data subject, thus the processing of health data is associated with the observance of the principles of legality, necessity and proportionality.⁷

¹ World Medical Association, *WMA Declaration of Lisbon on the Rights of the Patient*, 2022. https://www.wma.net/policies-post/wma-declaration-of-lisbon-on-the-rights-of-the-patient/?utm_source=10.01.2026.

² European Convention on Human Rights, Rome, 4 November 1950, Article 8. https://fra.europa.eu/en/law-reference/european-convention-human-rights-article-8-0?utm_source=10.01.2026.

³ *Z v. Finland*, no. 22009/93, ECHR, 1997 <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#%7B%22itemid%22%3A%22001-58033%22%7D> (10.01.2026).

⁴ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), Article 9. <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-9-gdpr/> (10.01.2026).

⁵ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, *Handbook on European Data Protection Law*, 2018, <https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2018/handbook-european-data-protection-law-2018-edition> (10.01.2026).

⁶ Council of Europe, Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine (Oviedo Convention), ETS No. 164, 4 April 1997, Articles 10 and 26. <https://rm.coe.int/168007cf98> (10.01.2026).

⁷ Law of Georgia "On Personal Data Protection", 2023, Articles 3,4,6

According to the Law of Georgia "On Patients' Rights", medical records and any information about the patient related to diagnostics, treatment or the fact of providing medical services constitute confidential information, the protection of which is the obligation of the medical service provider both during the patient's lifetime and after his or her death. Disclosure of health data is permissible only in strictly defined cases, including with the patient's consent, in the event of the necessity to protect the life or health of a third party, or on other grounds directly provided for by law. In addition, the law, in parallel with the protection of confidentiality, develops the patient's right to information and decision-making, which creates a close connection between the protection of health data and the realization of patient autonomy. The patient has the right to determine to whom and in what volume information about his health condition is provided, and the provider of medical services is obliged to provide information taking into account the patient's ability to perceive and to use a minimum of special terminology.⁸ Such Georgian regulation once again confirms that health data is considered in Georgian law as information of particular sensitivity, the processing of which is related to the observance of the principles of legality, necessity and proportionality. The mentioned norms present the national model of health data protection as a complex legal institution oriented on the rights of the patient.

The Law of Georgia "On Health Protection" considers the issue of health data protection not only in the context of the individual rights of the patient, but also as an integral element of the ethical and professional framework of medical activity. The law defines medical (medical) secret as information that a doctor and other medical personnel receive in the process of professional activity about the patient's physical and mental condition, personal and family life, as well as the fact of providing medical care. This construction emphasizes that the protection of health data is not only a formal requirement of confidentiality, but also an ethical obligation of the medical profession, the violation of which entails legal liability.⁹ Thus, the legal regime for the protection of health data in the field of health care is based on a common principle of respect for human dignity, patient autonomy and professional responsibility.

1.4. Doctrinal foundations of health data protection (Faden & Beauchamp)

The scientific literature emphasizes that the special legal status of health data is determined not only by their sensitive content, but also by the context in which they are processed. According to Faden and

Beauchamp, the medical relationship is characterized by a structural power asymmetry between the doctor and the patient, where the patient is often in a physically, psychologically and informationally vulnerable position. In such conditions, the processing of a patient's health data is associated with an increased risk of their misuse and violation of patient autonomy, which justifies the existence of a strengthened legal regime for data protection. Accordingly, the confidentiality of health data and strict legal control over their processing are considered not only as a technical regulation, but also as a necessary tool for protecting the patient's dignity and self-determination.¹⁰

The considered normative and doctrinal analysis confirms that health data are considered in modern legal systems as a special category of personal data, the protection of which is based on the principles of human dignity and inviolability of private life. The synthesis of international and national regulations demonstrates that the protection of health data is a complex legal institution based on patient autonomy and professional responsibility and is not limited to technical requirements of confidentiality. Accordingly, the processing of such data is permissible only with strict observance of the principles of legality, purposefulness and proportionality.

Chapter 2. Legal bases for processing patient personal data in medical activities

2.1. Differentiation of legal bases: general bases and special categories of data

The processing of patient personal data, especially health information, in medical activities is permissible only if there are strictly defined legal bases. Modern data protection law rejects a single or formal legitimization of data processing and establishes the principle that each processing operation requires an independent, clearly defined and foreseeable legal basis. This approach is particularly strict in relation to special categories of personal data, among which patient health data occupy a central place.¹¹

The systematization of legal bases in European data protection law is most fully established in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which clearly distinguishes between general legal bases for data processing and additional conditions for processing special categories of data, thus clearly indicating that the processing of health data cannot be satisfied solely by the presence of the patient's will or administrative expediency.¹² Data processing in medical activities is legitimate only if both general and specific legal requirements are met simultaneously.

<https://www.matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/5827307?publication=8> (10.01.2026).

⁸ Law of Georgia on "Patient's Rights", 2000, Articles 27, 28, 21, 19

<https://www.matsne.gov.ge/document/view/16978?publication=16> (10.01.2026).

⁹ Law of Georgia "On Health Protection", 1997, Articles 3, 4, 42.

<https://www.matsne.gov.ge/document/view/29980?publication=62> (10.01.2026).

¹⁰ Faden, R. R., Beauchamp, T. L., *A History and Theory of Informed Consent*, Oxford University Press, 1986. https://archive.org/details/historytheoryofi0000fade/page/n5/mode/2up?utm_source (10.01.2026).

¹¹ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, *Handbook on European Data Protection Law*, 2018, <https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2018/handbook-european-data-protection-law-2018-edition> (10.01.2026).

¹² Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), Article 6, 9. <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-6-gdpr/> <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-9-gdpr/> (10.01.2026).

One of the main legal bases in the medical field is the fulfillment of a legal obligation. Medical institutions and healthcare professionals are obliged to maintain patient medical records, store diagnostic and treatment data, and ensure access to information for the purposes of supervision and accountability. Such processing is not based on the patient's consent, but on the existence of a public-legal obligation and constitutes an independent legal basis for data processing.¹³

The second important legal basis is related to the necessity of protecting life and health, which becomes particularly relevant in emergency medical care, critical situations and cases where the patient is unable to express his/her will. The legal logic is based on the principle that the protection of life and health constitutes the highest legal value, which justifies the processing of personal data without consent, but only under strict proportionality conditions.¹⁴ This basis is widely recognized in both European and national legal frameworks.

The third legal basis is related to the public interest in the field of health protection. Public health surveillance is a form of state responsibility, the implementation of which often requires the systematic collection, analysis and sharing of personal data, since the implementation of public health policies, epidemiological control, disease prevention and ensuring the efficiency of the healthcare system are impossible without the processing of a certain amount of patient data. In such cases, data processing is permissible without informed consent, provided that it serves a clearly defined legitimate aim, is carried out proportionately and is accompanied by effective legal and institutional safeguards to prevent data misuse. Thus, data processing justified in the interest of public health does not abolish the requirement for the protection of privacy, but develops it within the framework of a legal model based on responsibility.¹⁵

2.2. Public interest

The case-law of the European Court of Human Rights confirms that health data, especially sensitive medical information, constitute one of the most protected areas of private life. In the case of *Z v. Finland*, the Court emphasised that the confidentiality of health data constitutes an essential element of Article 8 of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights

and Fundamental Freedoms and that its restriction is permissible only when there is an overriding public interest and strict legal safeguards are provided to prevent abuse. According to the Court, the disclosure of health data, including for the purposes of criminal proceedings or the protection of public health, cannot be legitimate automatically and requires a strict proportionality test. Thus, the case-law of the Court confirms that the processing of data justified by public interest does not override the principle of confidentiality, but requires its balancing with the effective protection of individual rights.¹⁶

2.3. Informed consent

Informed consent is one of the, but not universal, legal bases for data processing. The institution of informed consent is considered in modern medical law as a legal expression of patient autonomy and personal self-determination, which ensures the patient's participation in the decision-making process.¹⁷ Its function is not limited to the formal provision of information, but also includes a level of communication with the patient that enables a real understanding of the content, risks and alternatives of medical intervention.¹⁸

In the Georgian legal system, informed consent of the patient is established as one of the fundamental prerequisites for the legality of medical intervention and an important tool for protecting patient rights.¹⁹ The Georgian Law on Health Protection links informed consent to the voluntary acceptance of medical intervention by the patient or his/her legal representative on the basis of appropriate information and establishes its mandatory nature in various medical processes, including treatment, diagnostic, rehabilitation, preventive and palliative care. In the same context, the Georgian Law on Patient Rights considers informed consent as the result of a patient's informed decision, which is based on receiving complete information about the nature of the medical service, risks, expected consequences and alternative options, and in the case of minors, the participation of their legal representative.²⁰

The Georgian Law on Personal Data Protection links informed consent to the legal regime for protecting the confidentiality of patient health data and considers it as one of the important grounds for data processing in relation to special categories of data.²¹

¹³ General Medical Council (UK), *Confidentiality: good practice in handling patient information*, 2017

<https://www.gmc-uk.org/ethical-guidance/ethical-guidance-for-doctors/confidentiality> (10.01.2026).

¹⁴ Council of Europe, *Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine (Oviedo Convention)*, ETS No. 164, 4 April 1997, Articles 10 and 26. <https://rm.coe.int/168007cf98> (10.01.2026).

¹⁵ World Health Organization, *Ethical issues in public health surveillance*, 2017 https://www.asset-scienceinsociety.eu/sites/default/files/9789241512657-eng.pdf?utm_source (10.01.2026).

¹⁶ *Z v. Finland*, no. 22009/93, ECHR, 1997 <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#%7B%22itemid%22:%5B%22001-58033%22%7D> (10.01.2026).

¹⁷ Faden, R. R., Beauchamp, T. L., *A History and Theory of Informed Consent*, Oxford University Press, 1986.

https://archive.org/details/historytheoryofi0000fade/page/n5/mode/2up?utm_source (10.01.2026).

¹⁸ Morton, S. Janula, M. Quarto, C. *Trenfield, Sarah. Informed consent: do we have an obligation to double check?* National Library of Medicine, 2024, DOI: 10.1016/j.bja.2024.09.013.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/39426920/> (10.01.2026).

¹⁹ Law of Georgia "On Health Protection", 1997, Article 22, 23

<https://www.matsne.gov.ge/document/view/29980?publication=62> (10.01.2026).

²⁰ Law of Georgia on "Patient's Rights", 2000, Articles 4-6 <https://www.matsne.gov.ge/document/view/16978?publication=16> (10.01.2026).

²¹ Law of Georgia "On Personal Data Protection", 2023, Articles 6,8,9

The draft European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation also confirms that the patient's consent and the ability to refuse data processing do not constitute an absolute legal barrier, as the processing of health data for the purposes of public health, scientific research and policy development is permissible within the framework of exceptions defined by law.²²

Chapter 3. Forms of liability and administrative response in case of violation of the protection of patient personal data

3.1. Systemic framework of liability

Illegal or improper processing of patient personal data, especially health data, in medical activities gives rise to multi-level legal liability. Modern data protection law considers liability not only as an instrument of sanction, but also as an instrument of prevention and accountability. In this context, the liability framework includes administrative, civil and disciplinary responses, and in severe cases - criminal liability.²³

In the medical sector, administrative liability is often associated with violations such as: non-existent or incorrect legal basis for data processing; formal use of consent without its freedom and revocation; violation of the principles of data minimization and purposefulness; improper technical and organizational security measures.²⁴

Administrative liability is the central mechanism for responding to data protection breaches. The GDPR establishes a model of independent supervisory authorities, which are empowered to monitor, issue binding instructions and impose administrative sanctions on data processors.²⁵ According to the Regulation, the sanction must be effective, proportionate and dissuasive, which emphasizes the preventive function of administrative response.²⁶

3.2. Georgian administrative practice

In the legal space of Georgia, administrative response is carried out by the State Service for Personal Data Protection. National legislation does not limit violations of data processing rules to a declaration of principles and establishes a clear mechanism of administrative liability. In particular, the law distinguishes between separate liability for: violation of data processing principles, data processing without

legal basis, and processing of special categories of data (including health data) without basis, which, through the severity of the sanction, emphasizes the high-risk nature of health data processing. The sanctioning system is differentiated according to the type of entity and economic scale (annual turnover up to/above 500,000 GEL) and provides for both warnings and fines, as well as increased liability in the presence of aggravating circumstances.²⁷

In addition, the law extends liability not only to violations of the “basic” rules, but also to specific obligations that are particularly relevant in the medical field: compliance with video/audio monitoring rules, rules for processing data of deceased persons, violation of data subject rights, failure to comply with the obligation to inform, violation of security obligations, failure to comply with the obligation to notify and inform about an incident,²⁸ and obstruction of the activities of the supervisory authority or failure to comply with a request.²⁹ As a result, the law creates a complex framework for administrative response, where a violation of patient data protection is assessed not only from an ethical or civil-legal perspective, but also as a real instrument of public-legal liability, which obliges medical institutions and professionals to conduct data processing processes in advance in a legal manner.

The practice of the State Service for Personal Data Protection clearly shows that the processing of personal data of patients, especially health information, in the healthcare sector is subject to strict legal control and cannot be legitimized either by the reputational interest of the institution or by a general reference to the public interest. Both the disclosure of a patient’s medical record to a third party as a result of inadequate security and the public discussion of the patient’s health status by doctors during a press conference constituted the processing of a special category of data in violation of the requirements of the law.³⁰

A brief overview of two specific cases is important to illustrate national administrative practice:

Case I - Disclosure of a patient’s medical card: Based on the application of the data subject, the Personal Data Protection Service investigated the fact of a possible disclosure of a patient’s personal data by a private clinic. During the inspection, it was

<https://www.matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/5827307?publication=8> (10.01.2026).

²² Szikley, J. *European Health Data Space*, (“EHDS”) [https://journal.pdps.ge/doc/%E1%83%9F%E1%83%A3%E1%83%A0%E1%83%9C%E1%83%90%E1%83%9A%E1%83%98%201-2%20\(2025\)%20244-251.pdf](https://journal.pdps.ge/doc/%E1%83%9F%E1%83%A3%E1%83%A0%E1%83%9C%E1%83%90%E1%83%9A%E1%83%98%201-2%20(2025)%20244-251.pdf) (10.01.2026).

²³ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, *Handbook on European Data Protection Law*, 2018, <https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2018/handbook-european-data-protection-law-2018-edition> (10.01.2026).

²⁴ World Health Organization, *Ethical issues in public health surveillance*, 2017, https://www.asset-scienceinsociety.eu/sites/default/files/9789241512657-eng.pdf?utm_source (10.01.2026).

²⁵ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), Article 6, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-6-gdpr/> (10.01.2026).

²⁶ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), Article 83 <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-83-gdpr/> (10.01.2026).

²⁷ Law of Georgia “On Personal Data Protection“, 2023, Articles 66-68

<https://www.matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/5827307?publication=8> (10.01.2026).

²⁸ Law of Georgia “On Personal Data Protection“, 2023, Articles 69-79

<https://www.matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/5827307?publication=8> (10.01.2026).

²⁹ Law of Georgia “On Personal Data Protection“, 2023, Articles 86-87

<https://www.matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/5827307?publication=8> (10.01.2026).

³⁰ State Service for Personal Data Protection, *Processing of Personal Data in the Healthcare Sector (Case Review)*, 2023 <https://pdps.ge/ka/content/980/7252/jandacvis-sektorSi-personaluri-monacemebis-damuSaveba> (10.01.2026).

established that a photograph of the first page of the patient's inpatient medical card, which contained the patient's personal number, first and last name, contact information, name of the medical institution, date of admission to the clinic and other identifiable data, was sent to the patient by a third party via a social network. The Service determined that the clinic failed to ensure proper data security measures, which is why it was held administratively liable under Article 46, Paragraph 1 of the Law of Georgia on Personal Data Protection. In addition, it was established that the natural person processing the data processed the data for clearly personal purposes, which is why the law did not apply to the said action.³¹

Case II – Disclosure of patient data during a press conference – The Personal Data Protection Service, based on a notification, examined the legality of the clinic's disclosure of the patient's personal data during a press conference. As a result of the inspection, it was determined that the clinic's doctors publicly disclosed the patient's personal data, including information about his health condition. The Service determined that some of the information disclosed during the press conference had not previously been publicly known and the clinic possessed the most recent data on the patient's health. In addition, the patient's written consent to the disclosure of the data did not exist, and in accordance with the requirements of Article 6 of the Law of Georgia "On Personal Data Protection", the disclosure of special categories of data without consent is not permitted. Based on the above, the clinic was held administratively liable for the violation provided for in Article 45 of the same Law.³²

3.3. Georgian Judicial Practice

Georgian judicial practice on the issue of informed consent of the patient is limited, although individual decisions of the Supreme Court of Georgia emphasize the procedural, rather than formal, nature of consent. In one case, the court attached importance to the fact that the patient signed the consent document several hours before the operation, in an unstable psycho-emotional state, and concluded that the obligation to inform had not been properly fulfilled (SUSS, No. AS-645-2019).³³ In another case, despite the existence of a consent form, the court found that the patient was not informed about a possible serious complication of the operation, which actually developed after the operation (SUSS, No. AS-253-2021).³⁴ This practice confirms that consent should be assessed as a process of informing, and not only the existence of a written document.

3.4. Disciplinary liability and professional standards

Violation of the protection of a patient's personal data in medical practice often goes beyond legal

liability and directly concerns standards of professional ethics and integrity, since confidentiality is recognized as a fundamental principle of modern medical ethics and is an integral part of a doctor's professional responsibility.

Identifiable information about a patient's health is considered an essential element of privacy, the protection of which is an integral part of a doctor's professional responsibility.³⁵

Respect for the dignity, autonomy and rights of the patient is the core of the primary professional duty of the doctor, while the protection of confidentiality is a necessary prerequisite for a doctor-patient relationship based on trust. Special importance is attached to informed consent, which the Code considers not only as a prerequisite for medical intervention, but also as a legal and ethical guarantee of the patient's independent decision-making. At the same time, the Code clearly emphasizes the personal accountability of the doctor for the professional decisions made, the obligation to avoid conflicts of interest and the strict limitation of data disclosure only in cases of voluntary consent or exceptional ethical necessity. The above principles create the basis for disciplinary liability even in cases where the violation of patient data protection does not reach the threshold of administrative or criminal liability, which confirms that professional ethics in the field of medicine acts as an independent, but responsibility-oriented regulatory mechanism.³⁶

The confidentiality of a patient's personal data is both an ethical and legal obligation for medical personnel and serves to prevent the misuse of personal information. The standard developed by the UK's General Medical Council (GMC) obliges doctors to use only the minimum amount of data necessary, ensure the appropriate management and protection of patient information, and define in advance clear and justified criteria for possible disclosure of data. In addition, each decision on the use or sharing of data must be made taking into account the patient's rights and the principle of voluntary consent. The GMC's approach does not reduce confidentiality to just technical control over information, but links it to the doctor's personal professional responsibility for the entire data processing process, which strengthens professional order and helps to strengthen patient trust in the healthcare system. According to the document, deviations from confidentiality, including data disclosure, are permissible only in cases expressly provided for by law, in the presence of significant public interest or special necessity for patient safety, and always require strict legal and ethical justification.³⁷

3.5. Criteria for the effectiveness of administrative response

³¹ Ibid.

³² Ibid.

³³ Ruling of the Civil Cases Chamber of the Supreme Court of Georgia. No. AS-645-2019. 2019.

³⁴ Ruling of the Civil Cases Chamber of the Supreme Court of Georgia. No. AS-253-2021. 2021.

³⁵ World Medical Association, *Declaration of Lisbon on the Rights of the Patient*, adopted 1981, reaffirmed 2015,

<https://www.wma.net/policies-post/wma-declaration-of-lisbon-on-the-rights-of-the-patient/> (10.01.2026).

³⁶ World Medical Association, *International Code of Medical Ethics*, 1949 (rev. 2022) <https://www.wma.net/policies-post/wma-international-code-of-medical-ethics/> (10.01.2026).

³⁷ General Medical Council, *Confidentiality: good practice in handling patient information*, 2017

The effectiveness of the liability system in the field of patient personal data protection is not determined only by the severity of the sanctions imposed. The consistency of the administrative response, legal predictability, and a risk-oriented approach that takes into account the nature of the violation, the sensitivity of the data, and the vulnerable status of the patient are of decisive importance. Such an approach provides not formal, but real protection and the preventive function of liability in medical activities.³⁸

Disclosure of health information is permissible only in the presence of a specific and overriding public interest and requires a strict proportionality test, as such data are directly related to the patient's dignity, autonomy and trust in the health system.³⁹

The EHDS Regulation strictly limits the secondary use of health data and prohibits their use for discriminatory decisions, commercial marketing or other incompatible purposes, which underlines the preventive role of administrative supervision.⁴⁰

Chapter 4 - Technical and Organizational Obligations in Electronic Systems

4.1. Electronic Health Record System (EHR)

Electronic Health Record System (EHR) - The legality of health data processing in practice is closely linked to the normative framework for the functioning of the Electronic Health Record System (EHR). According to the current rule, the state is defined as the owner of the EHR, and access to the system is differentiated according to the roles of users, including the functional authority of the doctor, patient and authorized user. Access to the system is allowed only within the framework of the appropriate authorization and authority, which ensures the purposefulness of data processing and compliance with the principles of minimization. The same rule strengthens the technical elements of accountability, including the maintenance of a user register and logging of access to the system, which makes it possible to further control and legal verifiability of the data processing process.⁴¹

4.2. Register of Persons with Disabilities

The electronic system of the Register of Persons with Disabilities is a specialized model of health data

processing, which is based on strict differentiation of access. The functioning of the system is organized by the so-called “pages” model, within which different subjects — including the system owner, the authorized person of the medical institution, the doctor and the data subject — are granted different and purposefully limited access rights. Of particular importance is the fact that the doctor has access only to his own patient's data, which directly reflects the implementation of the “need-to-know” principle in practice and reduces the risk of improper use or excessive availability of health data.⁴²

4.3. Electronic Prescriptions

The electronic prescription circulation rule for pharmaceutical products (medicinal products) of the second group, Form No. 3, is a **special normative model for the processing of personal health data**, which establishes a centralized circulation of electronic prescriptions, within which access to data is differentiated according to the functional roles of users (doctor, pharmacist, patient) and is carried out only on the basis of appropriate authorization and professional authority. In addition, the electronic prescription system provides for the recording (logging) of the data processing process, access control and information storage rules, which ensures the technical and organizational foundations of data security, accountability and administrative supervision and strengthens the legal regime for the protection of health data.⁴³

The electronic prescription system for prescription of psychotropic drugs and medicinal products equivalent to pharmaceutical products under special control, Form No. 2, is functionally linked to the electronic prescription circulation rule of Form No. 3, which ensures a unified, transparent and controlled model for processing highly sensitive health data. Such regulation enhances the traceability and accountability of data processing and demonstrates that health data protection in Georgia is implemented not only through the general data protection law, but also through special sectoral digital regulations.⁴⁴

Conclusion

Persons with Disabilities“ Order No. 7/N of the Minister of IDPs from the Occupied Territories of Georgia, Labor, Health and Social Protection of January 31, 2024 <https://www.matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/6090865?publication=0> (10.01.2026).

⁴³ “On Approval of the Rules for Circulation of Form No. 3 Electronic Prescription for Pharmaceutical Products (Medicinal Products) Belonging to the Second Group“ Order No. 01-29/N of the Minister of Labor, Health and Social Protection of Georgia of July 26, 2016, <https://www.matsne.gov.ge/document/view/3329318?publication=9> (10.01.2026).

⁴⁴ “On Approval of the Rules for Circulation of Electronic Prescription Form No. 2 for Psychotropic Medicines and Medicinal Products Equivalent to Pharmaceutical Products Subject to Special Control“ Order No. 01-31/N of the Minister of IDPs from the Occupied Territories of Georgia of April 8, 2022, <https://www.matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/5433415?publication=1> (10.01.2026).

<https://www.gmc-uk.org/ethical-guidance/ethical-guidance-for-doctors/confidentiality> (10.01.2026).

³⁸ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), Article 5,6,9,83 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj> (10.01.2026).

³⁹ European Court of Human Rights, *Z v. Finland*, no. 22009/93, Judgment of 25 February 1997 <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-58033> (10.01.2026).

⁴⁰ Szikley, J. *European Health Data Space*, (“EHDS”) [https://journal.pdps.ge/doc/%E1%83%9F%E1%83%A3%E1%83%A0%E1%83%9C%E1%83%90%E1%83%9A%E1%83%98%201-2%20\(2025\)%20244-251.pdf](https://journal.pdps.ge/doc/%E1%83%9F%E1%83%A3%E1%83%A0%E1%83%9C%E1%83%90%E1%83%9A%E1%83%98%201-2%20(2025)%20244-251.pdf) (10.01.2026).

⁴¹ “On Determining the Procedure for the Operation and Production of the Electronic Health Records System (EHR)“ Order No. 01-1/N of the Minister of IDPs from the Occupied Territories of Georgia, Labor, Health and Social Protection of January 3, 2019, <https://www.matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/4390457?publication=11> (10.01.2026).

⁴² “On Approval of the Rules for the Operation and Maintenance of the Electronic System of the Register of

The present study has confirmed that the processing of patient health data in medical practice is a high-risk legal process that is directly related to the protection of human dignity, privacy and patient autonomy. A comparative analysis of international and national legal frameworks reveals that health data are considered a special category of personal data in modern legal systems, the processing of which is permissible only under strictly defined legal grounds and under conditions of enhanced protection.

The study has shown that informed consent, despite its fundamental importance, cannot act as a universal legitimizer of health data processing and cannot abolish the principles of purposefulness, minimization and security of data. The formal existence of consent does not exclude the responsibility of the data processor and requires an assessment of its procedural, voluntary and substantive nature.

The case law of the European Court of Human Rights and European data protection standards confirm that the confidentiality of health data is one of the most intensive areas of privacy protection and its restriction is permissible only by passing a test of overriding public interest and strict proportionality, which excludes the automatic legitimization of data processing by a general reference to public interest.

The analysis of the administrative practice of Georgia has shown that violations of patient data protection are in most cases related to the improper legal and organizational arrangement of data processing processes, which is why administrative liability functions not only as a sanctioning but also as a preventive mechanism.

Finally, the study confirms that the effective implementation of patient health data protection requires the unified and systematic operation of legal, institutional and technical-organizational mechanisms and cannot be limited to meeting formal normative requirements.

In view of the above, it is advisable to formulate recommendations that ensure the real and effective implementation of data protection principles in medical practice:

- **Differentiation of informed consent** - It is recommended to clearly separate the informed consent of the patient from other legal grounds for data processing. Consent should be assessed as a procedural legal mechanism and not as a universal basis for data processing, especially in relation to special categories of data. This approach is based on the principles of legality and accountability and reduces the risk of formal use of consent.

- **Institutionalization of the proportionality test** - When processing health data in the public interest, it is recommended to systematically apply the proportionality test, which includes an assessment of the legitimate aim, necessity and scope of the restriction. This test should become a standard tool for both administrative and judicial control, which is consistent with the approach established by the case law of the European Court of Human Rights.

- **Strengthening the principle of accountability** - Data processors should be obliged not only to comply

with data protection rules, but also to prove their compliance. This includes prior documentation of data processing processes, logging of access, regular review of security measures and risk-oriented management.

- **Legal integration of technical and organizational measures** - It is recommended to directly link technical and organizational security measures with legal requirements when operating electronic systems (EHR, registries, electronic prescriptions). This ensures traceability of data processing, administrative control and effective implementation of responsibility.

- **Strengthening professional ethics and disciplinary responsibility** - The protection of patient health data should be considered not only as a legal issue, but also as a matter of professional ethics. It is recommended to actively use disciplinary mechanisms in cases where a data protection violation does not reach the threshold of administrative or criminal liability, but violates the patient-trust relationship.

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